

The annotated checklist of plant species that occur in the wetland habitats of Georgia (the Caucasus)

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Abstract

The checklist includes 270 species that belong to 80 families and 183 genera. Each species has been annotated with the following information: life form, wetland indicator status, and location. In this checklist, Angiosperms are represented by 252 species (93.3%), Bryophytes – 10 species (3.7%), Pteridophytes – 8 (3%), Gymnosperms – 1 (0.4%). The largest families by the number of species are Cyperaceae – 39 (14.4%), Poaceae – 29 (10.7%), Rosaceae – 19 (7.1%), Asteraceae – 17 (6.3%), Fabaceae – 11 (4.1%) and Juncaceae – 11 (4.1%). The checklist is dominated by 55 Palaearctic species (20.4%), followed by 46 Holarctic (17.1%), 31 Euro-Mediterranean (11.5%), 31 Cosmopolitan (11.5%), and 27 Euro-Siberian (10.03%) species. The endemism rate is 4.8%, and the proportion of invasive and naturalized plants is 8.5%. Obligate wetland plants, mainly belonging to the families Cyperaceae and Juncaceae, make up 34.2% of the floristic composition. This is the first comprehensive published checklist of the flora of Georgian wetlands, annotated with wetland indicator values.

Key words

Chorotypes, Floristic composition, Life Forms, Wetlands, Wetland Indicator Status

Introduction

Wetland ecosystems are considered a natural resource of global importance. They provide many valuable ecosystem services, among them flood protection, water quality improvement, and carbon dioxide sequestration. Wetlands are home to thousands of plant and animal species (Verhoeven et al. 2006; Ramsar Convention Secretariat 2013), including endemic, relict, and rare species (Suppl. material 1, figs 1–3). Furthermore, the aesthetic and recreational benefits of wetlands are also important (Suppl. material 2, figs 1–3). Hence, the preservation of this ecosystem is of the utmost importance (Hazeu et al. 2010; Tedoradze et al. 2020). Many wetlands are threatened by eutrophica-

tion (Suppl. material 2: fig. 4) driven by both global and local factors, as well as habitat fragmentation and degradation (Verhoeven et al. 2006). Wetlands harbor many characteristic species, such as hydrophytes (Suppl. material 3, figs 1–2), which are often used as specific indicators for assessing the current condition of wetlands (Reed and Peters 1988; Lyon and Lyon 2011; Eggers and Reed 2015). Therefore, having a comprehensive checklist of wetland flora is the first necessary step for planning and executing the monitoring and conservation of wetlands in Georgia.

Georgia is a mountainous country adjacent to the sea, and such settings create steep climatic gradients, in which geographical location plays an important role (Kikvidze 2020). Therefore, we also performed a gradient analysis

of the species composition of wetland communities across Georgia using geographical coordinates and altitude as environmental variables.

Here we present the recorded and assessed 270 species as a list of plants found in different wetlands in most regions of Georgia. It should be noted that number of studies have been published on wetlands in Georgia, relating to different periods (Kimeridze 1966, 1985; Melia 1985; Kikvidze and Oshawa 2001; Denk et al. 2001; BSSGW 2008; Matchutadze 2008; Krebs et al. 2009; Matchutadze et al. 2015). However, there are practically no studies covering all the major wetlands, nor do we have any studies on the indicator status of typical wetland species recorded. Therefore, our study addresses these two needs.

Materials and methods

Georgia is a climatically diverse country owing to the adjacent Black Sea and high mountain chains of various orientations. Through our sampling regions, the mean annual temperature varies from 14 °C in Colchis to 3 °C in Kazbegi; annual precipitation varies roughly between 600 and 900mm and its distribution changes from almost ideally uniform in Imereti (760mm ± 15SD) to strongly seasonal in Sioni (812mm ± 45SD). Therefore, the study regions represent quite a diverse climatic character (Fick and Hijmans 2017).

Study regions are located at different hypsometric heights and in different climatic zones. In total, we sampled 218 plots in seven regions across Georgia (Fig. 1): Kolkheti Lowland (121 plots), Javakheti Plateau (53 plots), mountainous Adjara – the highlands of Adjara (8 plots), Kazbegi region (7 plots), Iori River Gorge – the northwestern part of Kakheti province (9 plots), Upper Imereti (6 plots), Shida Kartli Lowland (6 plots), and Alazani Valley (8 plots).

Fieldwork campaigns were conducted during the vegetation seasons of 2015–2017. The sampling locations were selected prior to our fieldwork using topographic maps of the Soviet period (1950–60s), which depicted mires, swamps, and other wetlands in a rather detailed manner. Before sampling, we determined the location and morphology of wetland bodies with 5m accuracy using RapidEye satellite multispectral imagery.

Sampling points on the pre-selected sites were located using navigation instruments – GPS and satellite images. First, we described the hydrological conditions of a given wetland by assessing its water surface: water not visible (0), well visible (1), and partly visible (2); we also assessed observable human impacts through three categories (low, intermediate, and high impacts).

Vegetation was sampled as follows: once a wetland was recognized and inspected, the team chose visually the most representative area(s) for sampling. A central point of circular plots was placed at random in a selected area, and radii for plots were delineated: a 9 meter-radius circular plot around a sampling point was used to sample trees; a 6 meter-radius plot was used for sampling shrubs, and a 3 meter-radius circle was used for sampling herbaceous plants (USACE 1987). Within these plots, we identified and recorded all detectable species and assessed their abundance

by the modified scale of Braun-Blanquet (r, +, 1, 2m, 2a, 2b, 3, 4, 5) (Braun-Blanquet 1964; van der Maarel 2007). Plant species were identified using the Key to Plants of Georgia (Ketskhoveli et al. 1964, 1969) and the Excursion Flora of Germany (Exkursionsflora von Deutschland) (Jäger et al. 2013). The plant species that were not easily identifiable in the field were collected and later accurately identified by comparing them to the specimens in the National Herbarium (TBI) of the Institute of Botany, Ilia State University, Georgia.

In all, we collected 216 herbarium specimens of 132 plant species (herbarium specimens will be available at the TBI). Latin names of taxa (families, genera, and species) are based on nomenclatural checklists of ‘Flora of Georgia’ (Gagnidze 2005; Davlianidze et al. 2018) and are harmonized with international plant databases (Euro+Med 2006; GBIF 2022; IPNI 2022; POWO 2022; WFO 2022). Species that are alien to Georgia are listed according to Kikodze et al. (2010).

Each species was ranked according to its wetland indicator status on the following scale (USACE 1987; Reed and Peters 1988; Lyon and Lyon 2011; Lichvar et al. 2013; Eggers and Reed 2015):

- Obligate wetland plants (OBL) – almost always occur in wetlands (estimated probability > 99%) under natural conditions.
- Facultative wetland plants (FACW) – usually occur in wetlands (estimated probability 67% – 99%), but is occasionally found in non-wetlands.
- Facultative plants (FAC) – equally likely to occur in wetlands (estimated probability 34% – 66%) or non-wetlands.
- Facultative upland plants (FACU) – usually occur in non-wetlands (estimated probability 67% – 99%), but are occasionally found in wetlands (estimated probability 1% – 33%).
- Obligate upland plants (UPL) – almost always occur (estimated probability > 99%) in non-wetlands under natural conditions.

Each species was assessed for its phytogeographical distribution (Komarov 1934–1960; Takhtajan 1954–2011, 2003–2012; Tutin et al. 1964–1993; Davis 1965–2001; Ketskhoveli et al. 1971–2011) and online international plant databases (GBIF 2022; Euro+Med 2006; POWO 2022). In addition, we used different regional works in this field to determine the chorotypes of the species (Gagnidze and Kemularia-Nathadze 1985; Portenier 1993, 2000; Gagnidze 2004; Shetekauri and Chelidze 2016; Lachashvili et al. 2020; Lachashvili et al. 2021; Tedoradze 2022). Plant life forms were determined using the LEDA Traitbase (Klotz et al. 2002). Endemics of the Caucasus are given after Solomon et al. (2013).

To analyze the variation of species composition on geographical gradients, we performed Canonical Correspondence Analysis (CCA). Statistical significance was computed with 999 permutation tests. We analyzed species with a frequency of occurrence in the community matrix equal to or greater than 5. For this purpose, we used PAST (v. 4.12) software (Hammer et al. 2001).

Figure 1. Map showing study sites/plots in Georgia.

Results and discussion

We sampled wetlands across the diverse landscapes of Georgia: the Black Sea coastal zone with a maritime climate, the inland lowlands with a dry and continental climate, high dry plateaus, and subalpine environments. Our results permitted us to construct an annotated checklist of the wetland flora of Georgia, which includes 270 species sampled from 218 pre-selected sites. Each species on the resulting checklist (Table 1) is annotated with the following data: life form, wetland indicator status, chorotype, and location (study regions). The coordinates of each plot can be found in the supplementary information, where the species presence-absence matrix is also included as Suppl. material 4.

The checklist includes 270 species belonging to 80 families and 183 genera. Angiosperms are the core of the floristic composition – 251 species (93%). Bryophytes are represented by 10 species (3.7%), Pteridophytes – 8 (3%), Gymnosperms – 1 (0.4%). Leading families by the number of species are Cyperaceae – 39 (14.4%), Poaceae – 29 (10.7%), Rosaceae – 19 (7.1%), Asteraceae – 17 (6.3%), Fabaceae – 11 (4.1%) and Juncaceae – 11 (4.1%). The floristic composition of Georgian wetlands is dominated by Palaearctic species 55 (20.4%), followed by Holarctic 46 (17.1%), Euro-Mediterranean 31 (11.5%), Cosmopolitan 31 (11.5%) and Euro-Siberian 27 (10.03%) species.

Out of 270 species, half are represented by only one or two sites. The most frequent species are *Alnus glutinosa* subsp. *barbata* – (69 sites), *Molinia caerulea* – (56 sites), *Juncus effusus* – (42 sites), *Carex vesicaria* – (40 sites), *Phragmites australis* – (37 sites), *Persicaria thunbergii* – (36 sites), *Sphagnum palustre* – (35 sites), *Lythrum salicaria* –

(32 sites), *Cladium mariscus* – (29 sites), *Frangula alnus* – (29 sites). Among the species listed above, five are OBL in wetlands, three – FACW, and of the remaining two, one – FACU and the other – FAC. The presence of the latter, among the ten most frequent species, indicates the current state of the wetland, which is often expressed by fragmentation and the spread of species uncharacteristic for wetlands.

The percent share of endemic species in the checklist is 4.8%; the rate of endemism is low compared to the flora of Georgia, where the endemism rate is approximately 31% (Solomon et al. 2013). There are 13 endemic species, four of which are endemic to Georgia and nine to the Caucasus. At the same time, we recorded 23 non-native species, which gives a rate (8.5%) higher than that of endemics. The low endemism rate in wetland vegetation is not surprising since the typical wetland species usually have a very wide distribution; wetland vegetation is often considered to be azonal (sensu Sieben 2019), with very little variable composition across large gradients within subcontinents such as Mexico (Ramos-Tapia et al. 2022) or South Africa (Mucina et al. 2006) or even between so distant places such as the western and eastern extremities of Eurasia (Kikvidze and Ohsawa 2001; see also Denk et al. 2001).

In the checklist, species that almost always occur in wetlands (OBL) and species that are commonly (FACW) found in wetlands together made up 52.1% of the total number of species (OBL – 92 and FACW – 48 species). Species that are equally likely to occur in wetlands or non-wetlands (FAC) made up 68 species (25.3%). The plants that usually occur in non-wetlands but are occasionally found in wetlands (FACU) consisted of 62 species (23.1%).

Table 1. Annotated checklist of plant species that occur in the wetland habitats of Georgia. **LF** (Life Forms): F – Ferns; H – Herbaceous; H(A) – Herbaceous (Aquatic); M – Moss; W – Woody; W(L) – Woody (Liana). **WIS** (Wetland Indicator Status): FAC – Facultative; FACU – Facultative upland; FACW – Facultative Wetland; OBL – Obligate. **Chorotypes**: Aus. – Native Australia; CA – Caucaso-Anatolian; Cau. – Caucasian; Cau.(EC) – Caucasian (Endemic of Caucasia); Cau.(EG) – Caucasian (Endemic of Georgia); CE – Caucaso – Euxinian; Cosm. – Cosmopolitan; Cosm.(ExPR) – Cosmopolitan (except polar regions.); Cosm.(MO) – Cosmopolitan/Mediterranean origin; Cosm.(SAMl) – Cosmopolitan/South America origin/invasive; Cosm.(TAF) – Cosmopolitan/Probably native to tropical Africa; CSWA – Caucaso-SW Asian; E – European; EA – East Asian; EA(I) – East Asian/invasive; EA(N) – East Asian/naturalized; EMed. – Euro-Mediterranean; EMed.(Cond.) – Euro-Mediterranean conditionally; ES – Euro-Siberian; ESWA – Euro-SW Asian; Eux. – Euxinian; HE – Hyrcano-Euxinian; Hol. – Holarctic; IT – Irano-Turanian; Med. – Mediterranean; Med. (Cond.) – Mediterranean conditionally; MSWA – Mediterranean-SW Asian; MSWAES – Med.-S.W. As.-Euras. Steppe; NA – North American; NA(Adv) – North American/adv-ventive; NA(I) – North American/invasive; NA(N) – North American/naturalized; Pal. – Palearctic; Pal.(W) – West Palearctic; Pal.(WW) – Palearctic/worldwide introduced; SA(N) – S American/naturalized; SEA – SE Asian; **Study Regions in Georgia**: 1 – Kolkheti lowland; 2 – Javakheti; 3 – Mtiiani Adjara; 4 – Mtiuleti; 5 – Iori River gorge; 6 – Upper Imereti; 7 – Shida Kartli lowland and Alazani Valley.

Family	Species	LF*	WIS**	Chorotypes	Study Regions in Georgia
Bryophyta					
Brachytheciaceae	<i>Brachythecium mildeanum</i> W. P. Schimper	M	OBL	Pal.	1
Climaciaceae	<i>Climacium dendroides</i> Weber & D. Mohr	M	OBL	Hol.	3
Mniaceae	<i>Plagiomnium ellipticum</i> T.Koponen	M	OBL	Hol.	3
Polytrichaceae	<i>Polytrichastrum longisetum</i> G.L. Smith	M	OBL	Hol.	3
	<i>Polytrichum strictum</i> Menzies ex Bridel	M	OBL	Hol.	3
Sphagnaceae	<i>Sphagnum capillifolium</i> Hedwig	M	OBL	Cosm.	1,3
	<i>Sphagnum imbricatum</i> Hornschuch ex Russow	M	OBL	Pal.	1,3
	<i>Sphagnum palustre</i> L.	M	OBL	Cosm.	1,3
	<i>Sphagnum papillosum</i> Lindberg	M	OBL	Hol.	1
	<i>Sphagnum platyphyllum</i> Warnstorff	M	OBL	Hol.	1
Pteridophyta					
Aspleniaceae	<i>Asplenium trichomanes</i> L.	F	FACU	Cosm.	1
Athyriaceae	<i>Athyrium filix-femina</i> (L.) Roth	F	FAC	Hol.	1
Dennstaedtiaceae	<i>Pteridium aquilinum</i> (L.) Kuhn (<i>P. tauricum</i> V. I. Krecz.)	F	FAC	Pal.	1
Dryopteridaceae	<i>Dryopteris filix-mas</i> (L.) Schott	F	FAC	Hol.	7
Equisetaceae	<i>Equisetum palustre</i> L.	H	FACW	Hol.	1,2,3,4,5,6,7
Lycopodiaceae	<i>Lycopodiella inundata</i> (L.) Holub (<i>Lycopodium inundatum</i> L.)	F	OBL	Hol.	4
Osmundaceae	<i>Osmunda regalis</i> L.	F	OBL	EMed.	1
Salviniaceae	<i>Salvinia natans</i> (L.) All.	F	OBL	Pal.(WW)	1,7
Gymnospermae					
Pinaceae	<i>Pinus pinaster</i> Aiton (<i>P. maritima</i> Du Roi)	W	FAC	Med.	1
Angiospermae					
Dicotyledonae					
Apiaceae	<i>Anthriscus sylvestris</i> (L.) Hoffm.	H	FACU	Pal.	4
	<i>Carum carvi</i> L.	H	FACU	Pal.	3
	<i>Daucus carota</i> L.	H	FACU	Pal.(W)	5
	<i>Eryngium caeruleum</i> M.Bieb.	H	FACU	IT	5
	<i>Eryngium campestre</i> L.	H	FACU	EMed.	1
Apocynaceae	<i>Periploca graeca</i> L.	W(L)	FACW	EMed.	1,7
	<i>Vinca major</i> subsp. <i>hirsuta</i> (Boiss.) Stearn (<i>V. pubescens</i> D'Urv.)	H	FAC	CA	1
Aquifoliaceae	<i>Ilex colchica</i> Pojark.	W(L)	FAC	Eux.	1
Araliaceae	<i>Hydrocotyle ramiflora</i> Maxim.	H	OBL	EA	1,3
	<i>Hydrocotyle vulgaris</i> L.	H	OBL	EMed.	1
	<i>Hedera colchica</i> (K.Koch) K.Koch	W(L)	FACW	CA	1
	<i>Hedera helix</i> L.	W(L)	FAC	ES	1,7
Asteraceae	<i>Achillea millefolium</i> L.	H	FACU	Hol.	2
	<i>Ambrosia artemisiifolia</i> L.	H	FACU	NA(I)	1
	<i>Arctium lappa</i> L.	H	FAC	Pal.	2,5
	<i>Artemisia absinthium</i> L.	H	FAC	Pal.	2
	<i>Bidens tripartita</i> L.	H	OBL	Hol.	1,3,5
	<i>Centaurea oxylepis</i> (Wimm. & Grab.) Hayek	H	FACW	EMed.	1
	<i>Cichorium intybus</i> L.	H	FACU	Cosm.	2,6
	<i>Cirsium arvense</i> (L.) Scop.	H	FACU	Cosm.	5
	<i>Cirsium obvallatum</i> (M.Bieb.) M.Bieb. (<i>C. obvallatum</i> (M.Bieb.) Fisch.)	H	FACU	Cau.	4
	<i>Cirsium vulgare</i> (Savi) Ten.	H	FACU	Cosm.	2
	<i>Eupatorium cannabinum</i> L.	H	FACW	EMed.	1,5
	<i>Inula helenium</i> L.	H	FAC	Pal.(W)	5
	<i>Pentanema britannicum</i> (L.) D.Gut.Larr., Santos-Vicente, Anderb., E.Rico & M.M.Mart.Ort. (<i>Inula britannica</i> L.)	H	FACW	ES	2,5
	<i>Petasites albus</i> (L.) Gaertn.	H	FACW	E	2
	<i>Solidago canadensis</i> L.	H	FACU	NA(N)	1,7
	<i>Taraxacum campyloides</i> G.E.Haglund (<i>Leontodon taraxacum</i> L.; <i>Taraxacum officinale</i> Weber ex Wiggins)	H	FACU	Pal.	2

Family	Species	LF*	WIS**	Chorotypes	Study Regions in Georgia
Betulaceae	<i>Xanthium strumarium</i> L.	H	FAC	Cosm.	1
	<i>Abnus glutinosa</i> subsp. <i>barbata</i> (C.A.Mey.) Yalt. (<i>A. barbata</i> C.A.Mey.)	W	FACW	Cau.(EC)	1,5,7
	<i>Carpinus betulus</i> L. (<i>C. caucasica</i> Grossh.)	H	FACU	EMed.	1
Brassicaceae	<i>Corylus avellana</i> L.	H	FACU	EMed.	1,7
	<i>Capsella bursa-pastoris</i> (L.) Medik.	H	FACU	Cosm.	1,2
Caprifoliaceae	<i>Nasturtium officinale</i> R.Br.	H	OBL	Cosm.	4
	<i>Cephalaria gigantea</i> (Ledeb.) Bobrov	H	FACU	Cau.	2
	<i>Dipsacus laciniatus</i> L.	H	FACU	ESWA	5
Celastraceae	<i>Valeriana alliarifolia</i> var. <i>tilifolia</i> (Troitsky) V.E.Avet. (<i>V. tilifolia</i> Troitsky)	H	FAC	Cau.(EG)	5
	<i>Euonymus europaeus</i> L.	H	FAC	EMed.	1,2,5
Ceratophyllaceae	<i>Ceratophyllum demersum</i> L.	H(A)	OBL	Cosm.	2
Convolvulaceae	<i>Convolvulus arvensis</i> L.	H	FAC	Pal.	1,5
Cornaceae	<i>Cornus sanguinea</i> subsp. <i>australis</i> (C.A.Mey.) Jáv. (<i>Swida australis</i> (C. A. Mey.) Pojark. ex Grossh.)	W	FAC	Eux.	1,5,7
Droseraceae	<i>Drosera intermedia</i> Hayne	H	OBL	Hol.	3
	<i>Drosera rotundifolia</i> L.	H	OBL	Hol.	1
Ebenaceae	<i>Diospyros lotus</i> L.	W	FAC	SEA	1
Elaeagnaceae	<i>Elaeagnus angustifolia</i> L.	W	FAC	Pal.	7
	<i>Hippophae rhamnoides</i> L.	W	FAC	Pal.	4
Ericaceae	<i>Rhododendron luteum</i> Sweet	W	FAC	Eux.	1
	<i>Rhododendron ponticum</i> L.	W	FAC	Eux.	1
	<i>Vaccinium arctostaphylos</i> L.	W	FACW	CA	1
Fabaceae	<i>Amorpha fruticosa</i> L.	W	FACW	NA(I)	1,5
	<i>Colutea orientalis</i> Mill.	W	FACU	CSWA	5
	<i>Gleditsia triacanthos</i> L.	W	FAC	NA(N)	1
	<i>Glycyrrhiza glabra</i> L.	H	FACU	Pal.(W)	5,7
	<i>Ononis arvensis</i> L.	W	FAC	Pal.(W)	5
	<i>Robinia pseudoacacia</i> L.	W	FACU	NA(I)	1
	<i>Trifolium canescens</i> Willd.	H	FACU	CSWA	2
	<i>Trifolium pratense</i> L.	H	FAC	Pal.	2,4
	<i>Trifolium repens</i> L.	H	FAC	Pal.	1
	<i>Trifolium spadicum</i> L.	H	FACW	ES	4
Fagaceae	<i>Vicia tenuifolia</i> subsp. <i>variabilis</i> (Freyn & Sint.) Dinsm. (<i>V. variabilis</i> Freyn & Sint.)	H	FACU	CSWA	1,5
	<i>Quercus hartwissiana</i> Steven	W	FAC	Eux.	1
Gentianaceae	<i>Quercus petraea</i> subsp. <i>iberica</i> (Steven ex M. Bieb.) Krassiln. (<i>Q. iberica</i> Steven)	W	FACU	CSWA	5
	<i>Gentiana septemfida</i> Pall.	H	FAC	CA	4
Hypericaceae	<i>Swertia iberica</i> Fisch. ex C.A. Mey.	H	OBL	Cau.(EG)	4
	<i>Hypericum mutilum</i> L.	H	FACW	NA(N)	1,2
Juglandaceae	<i>Hypericum perforatum</i> L.	H	FACU	Pal.	1
	<i>Pterocarya fraxinifolia</i> (Poir.) Spach (<i>Juglans pterocarpa</i> Michx.)	W	FACW	HE	1,7
Lamiaceae	<i>Lycopus europaeus</i> L.	H	OBL	ES	1,2
	<i>Mentha aquatica</i> L.	H	OBL	Cosm.	1,7
	<i>Prunella vulgaris</i> L.	H	FACU	Hol.	1
	<i>Stachys palustris</i> L.	H	OBL	ES	1,6
	<i>Thymus collinus</i> M.Bieb.	H	FACU	Cau.(EC)	2,5
	<i>Utricularia minor</i> L.	H	OBL	Hol.	1
Lythraceae	<i>Utricularia vulgaris</i> L.	H	OBL	Pal.	2
	<i>Lythrum hyssopifolia</i> L.	H	OBL	Cosm.	5
	<i>Lythrum salicaria</i> L.	H	OBL	Pal.	1,2,4,5,6,7
Malvaceae	<i>Trapa natans</i> L. (<i>T. colchica</i> Albov)	H(A)	OBL	Pal.	1
	<i>Hibiscus coccineus</i> (Medik.) Walter	H	FAC	NA(I)	1
	<i>Hibiscus ponticus</i> Rupr.	H	FACW	Cau.(EG)	1
	<i>Kosteletzkya pentacarpos</i> (L.) Ledeb.	H	FACW	EMed. (Cond.)	1
Menyanthaceae	<i>Menyanthes trifoliata</i> L.	H	OBL	Hol.	1,2,3
Moraceae	<i>Ficus carica</i> L.	W	FACU	IT	1
	<i>Morus alba</i> L.	W	FAC	EA	7
	<i>Morus nigra</i> L.	W	FAC	ESWA	1,7
Myrtaceae	<i>Eucalyptus cinerea</i> F.Muell. ex Benth.	W	FACW	Aus.	1
Nymphaeaceae	<i>Nuphar lutea</i> (L.) Sibth. & Sm.	H(A)	OBL	ES	1
	<i>Nymphaea alba</i> L.	H(A)	OBL	EMed.	1,2
Oleaceae	<i>Fraxinus excelsior</i> L.	W	FACU	ES	1,7
Onagraceae	<i>Epilobium montanum</i> L.	H	FAC	ES	4
	<i>Epilobium palustre</i> L.	H	OBL	Hol.	2,4
Orobanchaceae	<i>Euphrasia caucasica</i> Juz.	H	FACU	Cau.(EC)	4
	<i>Rhamphicarpa medwedewii</i> Albov	H	FACW	Cau.(EC)	1
	<i>Rhinanthus minor</i> L.	H	FACU	ES	4
Parnassiaceae	<i>Parnassia palustris</i> L.	H	OBL	Hol.	4
Phytolaccaceae	<i>Phytolacca americana</i> L.	H	FACU	NA	1,7

Family	Species	LF*	WIS**	Chorotypes	Study Regions in Georgia
Plantaginaceae	<i>Plantago major</i> L.	H	FAC	Hol.	7
	<i>Plantago media</i> L.	H	FAC	Pal.	2
Polygonaceae	<i>Persicaria hydropiper</i> (L.) Delarbre (<i>Polygonum hydropiper</i> L.)	H	OBL	Cosm.	3
	<i>Persicaria maculosa</i> Gray (<i>Polygonum persicaria</i> L.)	H	FACW	Pal.	1,2,6
	<i>Persicaria perfoliata</i> (L.) H.Gross (<i>Polygonum perfoliatum</i> L.)	H	FAC	EA(I)	1
	<i>Persicaria thunbergii</i> (Siebold & Zucc.) H.Gross (<i>Polygonum thunbergii</i> Siebold & Zucc.)	H	FACW	EA(I)	1,7
	<i>Polygonum carneum</i> K.Koch	H	FAC	CA	2
Primulaceae	<i>Lysimachia vulgaris</i> L.	H	FACW	Pal.	1,2,5
	<i>Primula auriculata</i> Lam.	H	FACW	CSWA	3
Ranunculaceae	<i>Clematis vitalba</i> L.	H	FAC	EMed.	1
	<i>Ranunculus caucasicus</i> M.Bieb.	H	FACU	Cau.(EC)	2
	<i>Ranunculus ophioglossifolius</i> Vill.	H	OBL	EMed.	2,5
	<i>Ranunculus trichophyllus</i> Chaix (<i>Batrachium trichophyllum</i> (Chaix) Bosch)	H	OBL	Hol.	2
Rhamnaceae	<i>Frangula alnus</i> Mill.	H	FAC	ES	1,7
	<i>Paliurus spina-christi</i> Mill.	H	FACU	MSWA	1
Rosaceae	<i>Agrimonia eupatoria</i> L.	H	FACU	Pal.(W)	1
	<i>Alchemilla sericata</i> Rchb.	H	FACU	Cau.(EC)	4
	<i>Comarum palustre</i> L.	H	OBL	Hol.	1,2,3
	<i>Crataegus microphylla</i> K.Koch	H	FAC	ESWA	1
	<i>Crataegus monogyna</i> Jacq. (<i>C. kyrtostyla</i> Fingerh. ex Schldt.)	H	FACU	ES	1
	<i>Filipendula vulgaris</i> Moench	H	FACU	Pal.	2
	<i>Fragaria vesca</i> L.	H	FACU	Hol.	7
	<i>Geum urbanum</i> L.	H	FACU	Pal.(W)	1,7
	<i>Malus sylvestris</i> subsp. <i>orientalis</i> (Uglitzk.) Browicz (<i>M. orientalis</i> Uglitzk.)	W	FAC	CSWA	1
	<i>Mespilus germanica</i> L.	W	FAC	EMed.	1
	<i>Potentilla erecta</i> (L.) Raeusch.	H	FACU	ES	1,3
	<i>Pyrus communis</i> subsp. <i>caucasica</i> (Fed.) Browicz (<i>P. caucasica</i> Fed.)	W	FACU	Cau.	1
	<i>Rosa canina</i> L.	W	FACU	Pal.(W)	1
	<i>Rubus caesius</i> L.	W	FAC	Pal.(W)	1
	<i>Rubus caucasicus</i> Focke	W	FACU	Cau.(EC)	1
	<i>Rubus caucasicus</i> Juz.	W	FAC	Cau.(EC)	1
	<i>Rubus hirtus</i> Waldst. & Kit.	W	FACU	EMed.	1
	<i>Rubus silesiacus</i> Weihe (<i>R. candicans</i> Weihe)	W	FAC	E	1
	<i>Spiraea japonica</i> L.f.	H	FACU	EA	1
	Rubiaceae	<i>Galium verum</i> L.	H	FACU	Pal.
Rutaceae	<i>Citrus trifoliata</i> L.	H	FAC	EA	1
Salicaceae	<i>Populus × canescens</i> (Aiton) Sm.	W	FACW	ES	7
	<i>Salix alba</i> L.	W	FACW	ES	5,7
	<i>Salix caprea</i> L.	W	FAC	ES	5
Sapindaceae	<i>Acer campestre</i> L.	W	FACU	EMed.	1,4,7
	<i>Acer negundo</i> L.	W	FACW	NA(Ad)	7
Simaroubaceae	<i>Ailanthus altissima</i> (Mill.) Swingle	W	FACU	EA(I)	5
Solanaceae	<i>Solanum dulcamara</i> L. (<i>S. persicum</i> Willd.)	H	FACW	Pal.	1
Ulmaceae	<i>Ulmus minor</i> Mill.	H	FAC	EMed.	1,7
Urticaceae	<i>Urtica dioica</i> L.	H	FAC	Pal.	5,7
Viburnaceae	<i>Sambucus ebulus</i> L.	W	FAC	EMed.	7
	<i>Sambucus nigra</i> L.	W	FAC	EMed.	1
	<i>Viburnum lantana</i> L.	W	FACU	EMed.	1
	<i>Viburnum opulus</i> L.	W	FACW	ES	1,7
Monocotyledonae					
Acoraceae	<i>Acorus calamus</i> L.	H	OBL	Hol.	1
Alismataceae	<i>Alisma plantago-aquatica</i> L.	H	OBL	Pal.	1,2,3,4,5,6
	<i>Sagittaria sagittifolia</i> L.	H	OBL	ES	1,2
Amaryllidaceae	<i>Allium</i> sp.	H	FAC	-	5
	<i>Pancratium maritimum</i> L.	H	FACU	Med.	1
Araceae	<i>Lemna minor</i> L.	H(A)	OBL	Cosm.	2,3,6
	<i>Lemna trisulca</i> L.	H(A)	OBL	Cosm.	1,2
Asparagaceae	<i>Asparagus officinalis</i> L.	H	FACU	ES	1
	<i>Ruscus aculeatus</i> L.	W	FAC	EMed.	1
	<i>Ruscus colchicus</i> Yeo	W	FAC	Cau.(EC)	1
Butomaceae	<i>Butomus umbellatus</i> L.	H	OBL	Pal.	2
Commelinaceae	<i>Commelina communis</i> L.	H	FAC	EA(N)	1
Cyperaceae	<i>Blismus compressus</i> (L.) Panz. ex Link	H	OBL	Pal.(W)	2,3,4
	<i>Bolboschoenus maritimus</i> (L.) Palla	H	OBL	Cosm.(ExPR)	1,5,7
	<i>Carex acuta</i> L.	H	OBL	ES	2
	<i>Carex aterrima</i> subsp. <i>medwedewii</i> (Leskov) T.V.Egorova (<i>C. medwedewii</i> Leskov)	H	FAC	CSWA	3
	<i>Carex canescens</i> L.	H	OBL	Hol.	1,2
	<i>Carex cespitosa</i> L.	H	OBL	ES	2

Family	Species	LF*	WIS**	Chorotypes	Study Regions in Georgia
	<i>Carex diluta</i> M.Bieb.	H	FACW	IT	4
	<i>Carex disticha</i> Huds.	H	OBL	EMed.	2,3
	<i>Carex divulsa</i> Stokes	H	FAC	EMed.	17
	<i>Carex echinata</i> Murray	H	OBL	EMed.	2,3
	<i>Carex elata</i> All.	H	OBL	EMed.	2,4
	<i>Carex hirta</i> L.	H	OBL	EMed.	2,4,5
	<i>Carex lachenalii</i> Schkuhr	H	OBL	Hol.	2
	<i>Carex lasiocarpa</i> Ehrh.	H	OBL	Hol.	1,2
	<i>Carex leporina</i> L.	H	OBL	ES	4
	<i>Carex limosa</i> L.	H	OBL	Hol.	2
	<i>Carex muricata</i> L.	H	FAC	ES	1
	<i>Carex nigra</i> subsp. <i>juncea</i> (Fr.) Soó (<i>C. juncella</i> (Fries) Th. Fries)	H	OBL	ES	3
	<i>Carex nigra</i> subsp. <i>transcaucasica</i> (T.V.Egorova) Jim.Mejías, G.E.Rodr.-Pal., Amini Rad & Martín-Bravo (<i>C. transcaucasica</i> T.V.Egorova)	H	OBL	CSWA	2
	<i>Carex pallescens</i> L.	H	FACW	Hol.	2
	<i>Carex panicea</i> L.	H	OBL	ES	1
	<i>Carex pendula</i> Huds.	H	FACW	EMed.	2
	<i>Carex pseudocyperus</i> L.	H	OBL	Hol.	2
	<i>Carex riparia</i> Curtis	H	OBL	EMed.	1,2,4
	<i>Carex rostrata</i> Stokes	H	OBL	Hol.	1,2,3
	<i>Carex tristis</i> M.Bieb.	H	FAC	CA	4
	<i>Carex vesicaria</i> L.	H	OBL	Hol.	1,2,3,4,7
	<i>Cladium mariscus</i> (L.) Pohl	H	OBL	Cosm.	1,2,7
	<i>Cyperus flavescens</i> L. (<i>Pycnus flavescens</i> (L.) P.Beauv. ex Rchb.)	H	FACW	Cosm.	1
	<i>Cyperus longus</i> subsp. <i>badius</i> (Desf.) Bonnier & Layens (<i>C. badius</i> Desf.)	H	FACW	Med. (Cond.)	3
	<i>Cyperus pannonicus</i> Jacq. (<i>Juncellus pannonicus</i> (Jacq.) C.B. Clarke)	H	FACW	Pal.	1
	<i>Cyperus serotinus</i> Rottb.	H	FACW	Pal.	1
	<i>Eleocharis palustris</i> (L.) Roem. & Schult.	H	OBL	Hol.	2,3
	<i>Eleocharis uniglumis</i> (Link) Schult.	H	OBL	Hol.	2
	<i>Rhynchospora alba</i> (L.) Vahl	H	OBL	Hol.	1
	<i>Rhynchospora caucasica</i> Palla	H	OBL	Cau.(EG)	1
	<i>Schoenoplectiella mucronata</i> (L.) J.Jung & H.K.Choi (<i>Scirpus mucronatus</i> L.)	H	FACW	Cosm.	1,2
	<i>Schoenoplectus tabernaemontani</i> (C.C.Gmel.) Palla (<i>Scirpus tabernaemontani</i> C. C. Gmel.)	H	OBL	Cosm.	2
	<i>Scirpus sylvaticus</i> L.	H	FACW	Pal.(W)	1,3,5
Hydrocharitaceae	<i>Elodea densa</i> (Planch.) Casp.	H(A)	OBL	SA(N)	1
	<i>Hydrocharis morsus-ranae</i> L.	H(A)	OBL	ES	1,7
Iridaceae	<i>Iris pseudacorus</i> L.	H	OBL	Pal.(W)	1,6,7
Juncaceae	<i>Juncus acutus</i> L.	H	FACW	EMed.	1
	<i>Juncus articulatus</i> L.	H	OBL	Hol.	1,2,4
	<i>Juncus atratus</i> Krock.	H	OBL	ES	2
	<i>Juncus bufonius</i> L.	H	FACW	Cosm.	1,3
	<i>Juncus conglomeratus</i> L.	H	OBL	Pal.(W)	2,3
	<i>Juncus effusus</i> L.	H	OBL	Cosm.	1,2,3,6,7
	<i>Juncus filiformis</i> L.	H	FACW	Hol.	2
	<i>Juncus inflexus</i> L.	H	FACW	Pal.(W)	4
	<i>Juncus maritimus</i> Lam.	H	FACW	EMed.	1
	<i>Luzula multiflora</i> (Ehrh.) Lej.	H	FACU	Hol.	2
	<i>Luzula stenophylla</i> Steud. (<i>L. pseudosudetica</i> (V.I.Krecz.) V.I.Krecz.)	H	FAC	CSWA	2
Juncaginaceae	<i>Triglochin palustris</i> L.	H	OBL	Hol.	4
Orchidaceae	<i>Spiranthes sinensis</i> (Pers.) Ames (<i>S. amoena</i> (M. Bieb.) Spreng.)	H	OBL	SEA	1
Poaceae	<i>Agrostis capillaris</i> L. (<i>A. tenuis</i> Sibth.)	H	FAC	Pal.	2
	<i>Agrostis vinealis</i> Schreb.	H	FAC	CA	2,5
	<i>Alopecurus aequalis</i> Sobol.	H	OBL	Hol.	2
	<i>Alopecurus arundinaceus</i> Poir.	H	FACW	Pal.	2
	<i>Anthoxanthum odoratum</i> L.	H	FAC	EMed.	2
	<i>Beckmannia eruciformis</i> (L.) Host.	H	FACW	Pal.	2
	<i>Bromus variegatus</i> M.Bieb. (<i>Bromopsis variegata</i> (M.Bieb.) Holub)	H	FACU	CSWA	4
	<i>Calamagrostis arundinacea</i> (L.) Roth	H	FAC	Pal.	2,5,7
	<i>Calamagrostis epigejos</i> (L.) Roth	H	FAC	ES	1,2,5
	<i>Calamagrostis pseudophragmites</i> (Haller f.) Koeler	H	FAC	Pal.	2
	<i>Cynodon dactylon</i> (L.) Pers.	H	FAC	Cosm.(Taf)	1,6,7
	<i>Dactylis glomerata</i> L.	H	FAC	Pal.	2
	<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i> (L.) P. Beauv.	H	FACW	Cosm.	1
	<i>Festuca drymeja</i> Mert. & W.D.J. Koch	H	FAC	MSWA	7
	<i>Koeleria luerssenii</i> (Domin) Domin	H	FACU	Cau.	4
	<i>Lolium rigidum</i> Gaudin	H	FACU	MSWA	2
	<i>Molinia caerulea</i> (L.) Moench	H	FACU	Pal.(W)	1,2,6,7
	<i>Nardus stricta</i> L.	H	FACU	Hol.	2,3,4
	<i>Oplismenus undulatifolius</i> (Ard.) P.Beauv.	H	FACW	Cosm.	1,7

Family	Species	LF*	WIS**	Chorotypes	Study Regions in Georgia
	<i>Paspalum dilatatum</i> Poir.	H	FACW	Cosm.(SAmI)	1,6,7
	<i>Paspalum distichum</i> L.	H	OBL	SA(N)	1
	<i>Phleum phleoides</i> (L.) H. Karst.	H	FACU	Pal.	2
	<i>Phleum pratense</i> L.	H	FACU	Pal.	3,4
	<i>Phragmites australis</i> (Cav.) Trin. ex Steud.	H	FACW	Cosm.	1,2,4,5,6,7
	<i>Poa annua</i> L.	H	FAC	Pal.(WW)	4
	<i>Scolochloa festucacea</i> (Wild.) Link	H	OBL	Hol.	2
	<i>Sorghum halepense</i> (L.) Pers.	H	FAC	Cosm.(MO)	1
	<i>Sporobolus fertilis</i> (Steud.) Clayton	H	FACW	EA(I)	1
	<i>Stipa pulcherrima</i> K.Koch	H	FACU	MSWAES	2
Potamogetonaceae	<i>Potamogeton crispus</i> L.	H(A)	OBL	Cosm.	1,2
	<i>Potamogeton natans</i> L.	H(A)	OBL	Hol.	1,2
	<i>Zannichellia palustris</i> L.	H	OBL	Cosm.	2
Smilacaceae	<i>Smilax excelsa</i> L.	W(L)	FACW	CE	1,7
Typhaceae	<i>Sparganium emersum</i> Rehmman	H	OBL	Hol.	1,2,3,6,7
	<i>Sparganium erectum</i> subsp. <i>neglectum</i> (Beeby) K.Richt. (<i>S. neglectum</i> Beeby)	H	OBL	Pal.(W)	1
	<i>Sparganium erectum</i> L.	H	OBL	Pal.(W)	5
	<i>Sparganium natans</i> L. (<i>S. minimum</i> Wallr.)	H	OBL	Hol.	2
	<i>Typha angustifolia</i> L.	H	OBL	Hol.	1,2,4,5,6
	<i>Typha latifolia</i> L.	H	OBL	Cosm.	1,2,6,7
	<i>Typha laxmannii</i> Lepech.	H	OBL	Pal.	1

Out of the 218 plots, 65 were taken in seasonally dry areas (water not visible), 37 were taken in fully water-covered habitats (water well visible), 113 – partially water-covered habitats (water hardly visible) and for three plots no data. It should be noted that we canceled a certain number of plots since we found different types of agricultural fields in places where, according to the old Soviet maps, there should have been wetlands.

According to the degree of human impact on the habitat, 46 plots were assessed as low (insignificant or not observed at all), 82 plots were assessed as intermediate (low impact rate), 89 plots were assessed as high (high anthropogenic impact), and for one plot there was no data.

During the fieldwork, we recorded *Drosera rotundifolia* for the first time in the Samegrelo region, where, together with the *Rhynchospora alba*, they make a unique plant community in the middle of the urbanized area (village Namikolaevo). This location is not mentioned for this species in the 'Flora of Georgia' (Ketskhoveli et al. 1971-2011), nor in the other reviewed literature. Regretfully, this unique habitat is in a very poor state owing to grazing by domestic animals and fragmentation, and it is possible that without proper protective measures it will disappear soon (see Suppl. material 2, fig. 5).

The presence of FAC and FACU species among the ten most frequently occurring species, the relatively low level of endemism against a high percentage of non-native species, and the assessment of 89 out of 218 sites as being under heavy human influence are indicative of the current challenging status of wetlands. The remaining undamaged wetlands with their highly diverse vegetation, distinctive relics, unique flora, and picturesque landscapes are impressive and can attract many visitors, provided such recreational and touristic activities are duly organized.

CCA axis 1 explained 63% of the variation in species distribution along geographical gradients, this axis was statistically highly significant ($p = 0.005$). The second axis explained 37% of this variation, yet it was insignificant ($p = 0.34$). Axis 3 could be dismissed as its explanatory power was very low (less than 1%, $p = 0.53$). The triplot (Fig. 2)

shows that axis 1 represents variation in altitude and longitude. Variation in latitude apparently does not play an important role as it is associated with the insignificant axis 2. Altitude in Georgia is tightly correlated with the mean annual temperature and can serve as its precise proxy, while longitude can be a proxy of precipitation (Kikvidze 2020). Therefore, perhaps the main climatic driver of species composition in the wetlands of Georgia is temperature, while precipitation might play a secondary role since the main feature of the wetlands is waterlogging, which can only weakly depend on precipitation.

Summary

Our study presents the most comprehensive checklist of Georgia's wetland flora compared to any previously published work. Importantly, we added an assessment of an indicator status, life forms, and chorotypes to each species, and the coordinates to each site in supplementary data in the form of a presence-absence matrix. The present list of plant species is based only on the results of field studies. The checklist includes 270 species belonging to 80 families and 183 genera. Among them are some non-native species that are not yet included in the 'Flora of Georgia' (e.g., *Eucalyptus cinerea*, *Pinus pinaster*, and *Hibiscus coccineus*). Angiosperms are the core of the floristic composition – 251 species (93%). Bryophytes are represented by 10 species (3.7%), Pteridophytes – 8 (3%), Gymnosperms – 1 (0.4%). Leading families by the number of species are Cyperaceae – 39 (14.4%), Poaceae – 29 (10.7%), Rosaceae – 19 (7.1%), Asteraceae – 17 (6.3%), Fabaceae – 11 (4.1%), and Juncaceae – 11 (4.1%). The floristic composition of Georgian wetlands is dominated by Palaearctic species 55 (20.4%), followed by Holarctic 46 (17.1%), Euro-Mediterranean 31 (11.5%), Cosmopolitan 31 (11.5%) and Euro-Siberian 27 (10.03%) species. Endemism is 4.8% and the proportion of invasive and naturalized plants is 8.5%. Obligate wetland plants, mainly belonging to the families Cyperaceae and Juncaceae, make up 34.2% of the floristic composition. Out of 270 species, half are represented

Figure 2. Wetland vegetation species composition along geographical gradients as analyzed with the CCA ordination; all data are well within the 95% confidence interval (encircled). “Eastern lowlands” include the wetlands in Shida Kartli Lowland and Alazani Valley; Iori Valley stands for the entire Iori River gorge.

by only one or two sites. The five most frequent species are *Alnus glutinosa* subsp. *barbata*, *Molinia caerulea*, *Juncus effusus*, *Carex vesicaria* and *Phragmites australis*. 52.1% of species belong to the OBL and FACW categories. Therefore, the main climatic driver of species composition in the wetlands of Georgia seems to be temperature, while precipitation plays a secondary role since the main feature of the wetlands is waterlogging, which can only weakly depend on precipitation.

Overall, our results indicate that the wetlands are under strong anthropogenic influence. We hope that this checklist will facilitate further work on completing the Georgian wetlands plant inventory.

დასკვნა

ჩვენი კვლევა წარმოადგენს საქართველოს ჭარბტენიან ჰაბიტატებში გავრცელებული სახეობების ყველაზე სრულ ნუსხას ადრე გამოქვეყნებულ შრომებთან შედარებით. რაც მთავარია, ჩვენ თითოეულ სახეობას მივანიჭეთ ჭარბტენიანი ტერიტორიების ინდიკაციის სტატუსი, სასიცოცხლო ფორმები და ქოროტიპები. ასევე მოცემულია თითოეული სახეობისთვის გავრცელების კოორდინატები ყოფნა-არყოფნის მატრიქსის სახით. ამასთან, მცენარეთა სახეობების არსებული სია ეყრდნობა მხოლოდ ველზე ჩატარებული აღწერების შედეგებს. ნუსხა მოიცავს 270 სახეობას, რომელიც გაერთიანებულია 80 ოჯახსა და 183 გვარში. ენდემიზმის პროცენტული მაჩვენებელი შეადგენს 4.8 %-ს, ხოლო ინვაზიური დანატურალიზებული სახეობები შეადგენს 8.5 %-ს. ჭარბწყლიანი გარემოსთვის დამახასიათებელი სახეობები შეადგენს საერთო რაოდენობის 34.2%-ს

და ძირითადად მიეკუთვნება Cyperaceae და Junca-ceae-ს ოჯახებს.

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Author contributions

GM planned the research; GT, GM, IA, NM, VM and ZJ conducted the field sampling; GT and TJ harmonized the nomenclature of species with international databases; GT and NL defined chorotypes; ZK performed the statistical analyses and led the writing; all authors critically revised the manuscript.

References

- Braun-Blanquet J (1964) Pflanzensoziozoologie, Grundzüge Der Vegetationskunde. 3 Aufl./J. Braun-Blanquet. Springer-Verlag, Wien-New York, 865 pp. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-7091-8110-2>
- BSSGW (2008) Botanical survey of south Georgian wetlands. BTC/SCP Pipeline Project, Georgia, Dzelkva Ltd., Tbilisi, 109 pp.
- Davis P (1965–2001) Flora of Turkey and the East Aegean Islands, Volumes 1–11. Edinburgh University Press, Edinburgh.
- Davlianidze M, Gviniashvili T, Mukbaniani M, Jinjolia-Imnadze L, Jugeli T (2018) Nomenclatural checklist of flora of Georgia. Universal, Tbilisi, 296 pp.
- Denk T, Frotzler N, Davitashvili N (2001) Vegetational patterns and distribution of relict taxa in humid temperate forests and wetlands of Georgia (Transcaucasia). *Biological Journal of the Linnean Society* 72: 287–332. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1095-8312.2001.tb01318.x>
- Eggers SD, Reed DM (2015) Wetland plants and plant communities of Minnesota and Wisconsin. US Army Corps of Engineers, Minnesota, 478 pp.
- Euro+Med (2006) Euro+Med PlantBase – the information resource for Euro-Mediterranean plant diversity. Published on the Internet. <http://ww2.bgbm.org/EuroPlusMed/> [Accessed 1 December 2022]
- Fick SE, Hijmans RJ (2017) WorldClim 2: New 1-Km Spatial Resolution Climate Surfaces for Global Land Areas. *International Journal of Climatology* 37(12): 4302–4315. <https://doi.org/10.1002/joc.5086>
- Gagnidze R, Kemularia-Nathadze L (1985) Botanical geography and flora of Racha-Lechkhumi. Metsniereba, Tbilisi, 147 pp. [In Russian]
- Gagnidze R (2004) Up to date problems and tasks of botanical geography of the Caucasus. *Notes on Plant Systematics and Geography* 44–45: 8–52. [In Russian]
- Gagnidze R (2005) Vascular Plants of Georgia – A Nomenclatural Checklist. Universal, Tbilisi, 247 pp.
- GBIF (2022) Global Biodiversity Information Facility. <https://www.gbif.org> [Accessed 1 December 2022]
- Hammer Ø, Harper DA, Ryan PD (2001) PAST: Paleontological statistics software package for education and data analysis. *Palaeontologia Electronica* 4(1): 1–9. https://palaeo-electronica.org/2001_1/past/issue1_01.htm
- Hazeu GW, Roupioz LFS, Perez-Soba M (2010) Europe's ecological backbone: recognising the true value of our mountains [Report 6/2010]. European Environmental Agency, Copenhagen, 225 pp.
- IPNI (2023) International Plant Names Index. The Royal Botanic Gardens, Kew, Harvard University Herbaria & Libraries and Australian National Herbarium. <http://www.ipni.org> [Accessed 1 December 2022]
- Jäger EJ, Müller F, Ritz CM, Welk E, Wesche K (2013) Rothmaler-Exkursionsflora von Deutschland, Gefäßpflanzen. Springer-Verlag, Berlin, 822 pp. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-8274-2723-6>
- Ketskhoveli N, Kharadze A, Kutateladze Sh (1964) The Key to Plants of Georgia. Vol. I. Metsniereba, Tbilisi, 458 pp. [In Georgian]
- Ketskhoveli N, Kharadze A, Kutateladze Sh (1969) The Key to Plants of Georgia. Vol. II. Metsniereba, Tbilisi, 506 pp. [In Georgian]
- Ketskhoveli N, Kharadze A, Gagnidze R (1971–2011) Flora of Georgia. Volumes 1–16. Metsniereba, Tbilisi. [In Georgian]
- Kikodze D, Memiadze N, Kharazishvili D, Manvelidze Z, Mueller-Schaefer H (2010) The alien flora of Georgia. Tbilisi, 36 pp.
- Kikvidze Z (2020) Ethnobiology of Georgia. Ilia State University, Tbilisi. 127 pp.
- Kikvidze Z, Ohsawa M (2001) Richness of Colchic vegetation: comparison between refugia of south-western and East Asia. *BMC Ecology* 1: 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1472-6785-1-6>
- Kimeridze K (1966) On the distribution pattern of wetland vegetation in the Caucasus. *Bulletin Academy of Sciences of the Georgian SSR* 43: 439–446. [In Georgian]
- Kimeridze K (1985) For the geobotanical study of alpine wetlands in the Caucasus. *Bioecology and phytocenology* 1: 48–76. [In Georgian]
- Klotz S, Ingolf K, Walter D, Gottfried B (2002) BIOLFLOR: Eine Datenbank Mit Biologisch-Ökologischen Merkmalen Zur Flora von Deutschland. Bundesamt für Naturschutz, Bonn 38: 1–334.
- Komarov V (1934–1960) Flora USSR. Volumes 1–30. Academy of Sciences of the USSR, Leningrad. [In Russian]
- Krebs M, Kaffke A, de Klerk P, Matchutadze I, Joosten H (2009) A future for Ispani 2 (Kolkheti, Georgia) and adjacent lands. *IMCG Newsletter* 2: 3–14.
- Lachashvili N, Eradze N, Khetsuriani L (2020) Floristic composition of pistachio-woodland (*Pistacia atlantica*) of Georgia (South Caucasus). *Flora Mediterranea* 30: 39–53. <https://doi.org/10.7320/FIMedit30.039>
- Lachashvili N, Eradze N, Kereselidze K (2021) Systematic structure and florogenetic connections of dendroflora of Tbilisi area (South Caucasus). *Flora Mediterranea* 31: 135–152. <https://doi.org/10.7320/FIMedit31.135>
- Lichvar RW, Banks DL, Kirchner WN, Melvin NC (2013) The national wetland plant list: 2013 wetland ratings. *Phytoneuron* 49: 1–241.
- Lyon JG, Lyon LK (2011) Practical handbook for wetland identification and delineation. Second Edition. CRC Press, Boca Raton, 196 pp. <https://doi.org/10.1201/b10804>
- Matchutadze I (2008) The vegetation cover of sphagnum peatlands of the Kolkheti Lowland. PhD Thesis, Shota Rustaveli State University, Batumi. [In Georgian]
- Matchutadze I, Bakuradze T, Tcheishvil T, Bolkvadze B (2015) Vegetation of Colchis Mires. *Earth Sciences* 4: 73–78. <https://doi.org/10.11648/j.earth.s.2015040501.23>
- Melia M (1985) Catalog of plants growing on boggy, wet, and saline soils in Georgia. State Committee of Agricultural Production of Georgia, 301 pp. [In Georgian]
- Mucina L, Rutherford MC, Powrie LW, Gerber J, Bezuidenhout H, Sieben EJJ, Cilliers SS, du Preez PJ, Manning JC, Hoare DB, Boucher C, Rebelo AG, Bredenkamp GJ, Siebert F (2006) Inland azonal vegetation. In: Mucina L, Rutherford MC (Eds) The vegetation of South Africa, Lesotho and Swaziland. SANBI, Pretoria, 616–657.
- Portenier N (1993) Geographic analysis of the flora of the Cherek Bezeni river basin (Central Caucasus). *Botanical Journal* 78(10): 16–22. [In Russian]
- Portenier N (2000) Methodological Issues of Defining the Geographical Elements of the Flora of the Caucasus. *Botanical Journal* 85(6): 76–84. [In Russian]
- POWO (2022) Plants of the World Online. Facilitated by the Royal Botanic Gardens, Kew. <http://www.plantsoftheworldonline.org/> [Accessed 1 December 2022]
- Ramos-Tapia I, Nuñez R, Salinas C, Salinas P, Soto J, Paneque M (2022) Study of Wetland Soils of the Salar de Atacama with Different Azonal Vegetative Formations Reveals Changes in the Microbiota Associated with Hygrophilic Plant Type on the Soil Surface. *Microbiology Spectrum* 10(5): e00533-22. <https://doi.org/10.1128/spectrum.00533-22>
- Ramsar Convention Secretariat (2013) The Ramsar Convention Manual: a guide to the Convention on Wetlands (Ramsar, Iran, 1971), 6th ed. Ramsar Convention Secretariat, Gland, Switzerland, 109 pp.
- Reed PB, Peters D (1988) National list of plant species that occur in wetlands: Northwest (Region 9). US Fish Wildlife Service, Washington, 89 pp.

- Shetekauri Sh, Chelidze D (2016) Flora of Meskheti and Javakheti (Lesser Caucasus). Saari, Tbilisi, 512 pp.
- Sieben EJ (2019) Zonal and azonal vegetation revisited: How is wetland vegetation distributed across different zoniomes. *Austral Ecology* 44(3): 449–460. <https://doi.org/10.1111/aec.12679>
- Solomon JC, Schatz GE, Shulkina T (2013) Red list of the endemic plants of the Caucasus: Armenia, Azerbaijan, Georgia, Iran, Russia, and Turkey. Missouri Botanical Garden Press, St. Louis, 451 pp.
- Takhtajan A (1954–2009) Flora of Armenia. Volumes 1–11. Academy of Sciences, Yerevan. [In Russian]
- Takhtajan A (2003–2012) Caucasian flora conspectus. Saint-Peterburg University press. Volumes 1–3. Russian Academy of Sciences, Moscow. [In Russian]
- Tedoradze G, Nakhutsrishvili G, Seip M, Theissen T, Waldhardt R, Otte A, Magiera A (2020) Terrain impacts the composition of the persistent soil seed bank: A case study of steep high mountain grasslands in the Greater Caucasus, Georgia. *Phytocoenologia* 50(1): 47–63. <https://doi.org/10.1127/phyto/2019/0321>
- Tedoradze G (2022) The importance of plant community structure and soil seed banks for productivity and sustainable use of pastures and hay meadows on the slopes in Khevi, a high mountain region in the Central Greater Caucasus. PhD Thesis, Ilia State University, Tbilisi.
- Tutin TG, Heywood VH, Burges NA, Valentine DH (1964–1993) Flora Europaea. Volumes 1–5. Cambridge University press, Cambridge.
- USACE (1987) Corps of Engineers Wetlands Delineation Manual (Technical Report No. Y-87-1). US Army Corps of Engineers, Vicksburg, 92 pp.
- van der Maarel E (2007) Transformation of cover-abundance values for appropriate numerical treatment-Alternatives to the proposals by Podani. *Journal of Vegetation Science* 18: 767–770. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/4499286>
- Verhoeven JTA, Beltman B, Bobbink R, Whigham DF (2006) Wetlands and natural resource management (Volume 190). In: Verhoeven JTA, Beltman B, Bobbink R, Whigham DF (Eds) Wetlands and Natural Resource Management. Springer Science & Business Media. 1–12. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-540-33187-2_1
- WFO (2022) World Flora Online. <http://www.worldfloraonline.org> [Accessed 1 December 2022]

Supplementary material 1

Images of some rare wetland species in Georgia

Authors: Tedoradze G 2023

Data type: image

Explanation note: Images of some rare wetland species in Georgia are given, including *Drosera rotundifolia*, *Rhynchospora alba*, *R. caucasica*, *Salvinia natans*, and *Trapa natans*.

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Link: <https://doi.org/10.3897/caucasiana.2.e101677.suppl1>

Supplementary material 2

Some wetland panoramas from different regions in Georgia

Authors: Tedoradze G 2023

Data type: image

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Supplementary material 3

Some characteristic wetland species in Georgia

Authors: Tedoradze G 2023

Data type: image

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Supplementary material 4

Coordinates of sampling sites, wetland characteristics

Authors: Tedoradze G et al. 2023

Data type: species data

Explanation note: Coordinates of sampling sites, wetland characteristics (such as water cover and anthropogenic impact), and presence-absence data for all plant species given in the check-list are provided.

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